

Santanam Wishal
How to fail professionally

Notion

When I wrote this book, I've been hit with a lot of failure. Even though it doesn't influence my life significantly. All the volunteer, university and work that I applied to, rejected me. I always hide under a *cheap* reason, knowing I'm the problem. Those cool LinkedIn profile just there to hide my failure. However, I'm still supported by my parents and my brother, both financially and mentally. **I am grateful for it.**

Notion

I failed. I fail too much. I failed too much. The environment demands me to be okay. I can't handle change. I can't keep being fake, being 'okay' and patience to everybody. I change because I'm forced to, not because I don't want to. Indeed, I changed, but my heart doesn't. It is there, in its mould. I write this book for me. To keep myself sane. If I decide to publish this, I hope this could help you to **fail professionally.**

Suicideal

As a failure, of course the urge to kms appeared very often. The only reason for me to not do that is my family and my friends. They truly care about me. They love me. I just can't make them cry. I love them too. In a discussion with my inner self, it said that **'nobody wants to die, they just want to run from their problems'**, that hits very hard on me, that no matter how much I failed, how much I shamed, there's still a part of me that wants to keep alive.

Switch Idea

Now I've solved half of the problems, by not run from it. I would face it. What's the worse could happened? Failed? I'm already familiar with it. I changed my mindset from fear of failure to **'you won't scared to failed if you're a failure'**. By changing this vision, I could see more opportunities than before. However, I'm still just a failure, that's something that I need to worked on.

Professional Failure

Because I've switched my perspective, I would need to change my method too. I start by doing small things with small chance to success. I expected it to be failed, every single time. And because I didn't expect to success, it won't be matter if I failed, because I expected it. This might sounds crazy, but for me, it is the best for my mental health. As Seneca said '**We suffer more in imagination than reality**'. We won't suffer if we expect to fail.

Professional Failure

Even though we expect to fail, doesn't mean we do the impossible things, but we do something that sounds impossible but not that really impossible if we put our effort maximally. ***If we fail? We expected it. And if we success? Congratulations, we fail to be failed.*** This is what I meant by being a professional failure. Not only give up and do not care about anything else, but to change your vision.

Professional Failure

To be honest, there is no proof that this method would success, I just thought about this yesterday and started doing this action with this vision today. There is no guarantee this would works. But I always believe that **'fortune favors the bold'**. This vision must be accompanied by outstanding effort. This book is a solution to the heart, to our mental. Not to our problems. I wish this book could help you to keep going.

LET

IT

HAPPEN

